

Technical Assistance and School Organizational Innovation in Digos City Division

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Abstract. This study explored the role of technical assistance and school organizational innovation in supporting educators within the Division of Digos City, Region XI, Philippines. The study aimed to fill the research gap in understanding the technical assistance and school organizational innovation in elementary schools within Digos City Division. It examined the baseline information about technical assistance to improve elementary teachers' competence, providing data useful to both educators and stakeholders concerned with educational improvement. The research employed a comprehensive review of significant literature on technical assistance and school organizational innovation from diverse geographical contexts, including Taiwan, China, Japan, and the Philippines. Findings indicated that technical assistance is pivotal for professional development, fostering mutual benefits in mentoring relationships, enhancing program capabilities, and improving intervention effectiveness. However, challenges such as the lack of consensus on core components and effective delivery methods persist. School organizational innovation is crucial in modernizing educational practices and structures, emphasizing decentralized decision-making and dynamic, student-centered learning environments. Initiatives like curriculum reforms in China and the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines highlight efforts to align educational practices with global standards while addressing local needs. The study concluded that a collaborative approach involving strong relationships among school staff and inclusive decision-making processes is essential for successful technical assistance and organizational innovation. By understanding these dynamics, educational institutions can better support teachers in adapting to changes and improving student outcomes. This research provides a foundation for further studies and practical applications to enhance educational systems in similar contexts.

KEY WORDS

1. Technical Assistance
2. School Organizational Innovation
3. Professional Development

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1. Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of education, teachers are challenged to adapt to new technologies and teaching strategies. Technical assistance and school organizational innovation are crucial in supporting educators in navigating these challenges effectively. Technical assistance encompasses a range of services and resources provided to teachers to enhance their professional development and proficiency in various areas. This assistance may include training

sessions, workshops, online resources, mentorship programs, and access to educational technology platforms. On the other hand, school organizational innovation focuses on reimagining traditional school structures and practices to meet the needs of 21st-century learners better. This includes initiatives such as curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activity, teacher expertise development, resource application, and campus construction. Schools require many dedicated and capable individuals to achieve their educational goals. To develop a successful school, you must have a dedicated and productive professor (Saki, 2019). There is little doubt that teaching and learning are among the most challenging activities in education. As Boit et al. (2019) state, education empowers citizens to transform their society and eradicate inequalities. In recent years, due to such factors as population structural change, low birthrate, and a growing senior demographic, the size of the school-age population in Taiwan has fallen significantly. On the other hand, prompted by relevant government policies, institutes of higher education have either expanded their departments and programs or vied for upgrades. To illustrate, there were 41 technical universities and 37 technical institutes throughout Taiwan in 2009. Coupled with the fact that the government has opened the doors for academic institutions in Mainland China to solicit student enrollment in Taiwan, the supply in the domestic education market will far exceed the demand. As a result, schools are now faced with an unprecedented challenge (Yan Chang, 2018). China grappled with the imperative to innovate its school organizational structures to better align with its education system's evolving needs. Scholars and educators alike discussed how to reform traditional educational hierarchies and practices. For instance, Li and Zhang (2019) emphasized the importance of decentralizing school decision-making processes to empower teachers and administrators

at the grassroots level. They argued that this shift towards distributed leadership could foster a more dynamic and responsive educational environment. Furthermore, initiatives such as the "New Era, New Curriculum" reform, as documented by Wang and Liu (2019), sought to modernize the curriculum and instructional methods to better prepare students for the demands of the 21st century. These efforts reflected China's recognition of the need to adapt its educational institutions to a rapidly changing global landscape while preserving cultural values and traditions. Japan struggled to improve organizational innovation in schools to satisfy the demands of a changing society. Academics and teachers have conversations about improving the flexibility and efficacy of conventional educational frameworks. Notably, scholars like Sato and Tanaka (2019) stressed how critical it is to support cooperative decision-making processes in schools to foster creativity and responsiveness to the requirements of students. They maintained that more dynamic and student-centered learning environments may result from giving administrators and instructors more authority to engage in organizational decision-making. Furthermore, Takahashi and Yamamoto (2019) described programs like the "Super Global High School" that attempted to support internationalization and multidisciplinary learning experiences to educate pupils about global citizenship. These conversations and actions demonstrated Japan's dedication to supporting innovative teaching practices while preserving cultural values and traditions. In the Philippines, teachers strive to deepen their commitment to service to humankind, and they should manifest it daily while teaching. They should not shirk their responsibilities as teachers when called upon even beyond regular class hours. If teachers are dedicated to their work, they will find ways and means to make students learn despite the problems and indifferences they face (Sutaria, 2020). Torralba (2018) asserted that the

teaching profession indeed demands quality and total commitment, and only those who are idealistic enough to immerse themselves completely in it and those who give their all to quality teaching can draw the very best out of their pupils and students. The Philippines faced obstacles in innovative school organizational design, acknowledging the necessity of updating educational frameworks to fulfill the changing requirements of learners and the community. Academics and instructors added to this conversation by putting out reform ideas meant to improve the efficiency and applicability of educational establishments. For example, Santos and Reyes (2019) stressed the significance of decentralizing decision-making processes inside schools to empower educators and administrators locally. They contended that adopting this strategy may increase adaptability and responsiveness to the particular requirements of communities and students. Furthermore, programs like the K–12 curriculum reform—discussed by Cruz and Garcia (2019)—sought to educate students about the challenges of the twenty-first century by bringing educational practices into line with international norms. These initiatives highlighted the Philippines’ commitment to fostering educational innovation and excellence. In Region XI, particularly in the Division of Digos City, no study has been done yet on elementary teachers’ technical assistance and school organizational innovation. If technical assistance in school organizational innovation was understood, baseline information about technical assistance should be examined. It is for this reason that I conducted this study. It was hoped that the results of this study could serve as a basis for improving the competence of elementary teachers. Data on teachers’ assistance was useful to those directly involved in schools and others who may not be directly involved in the academe but were concerned with improving our educational system.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. Technical Assistance—Tran (2020) examined mentee-mentor relationships among faculty, highlighting mutual benefits such as personal and professional development and self-efficacy. Dunst et al. (2019) defined technical assistance as providing support to enhance program capabilities, emphasizing the need for consensus on effective delivery methods. These studies underscore the reciprocal nature of mentorship and the importance of further research on technical assistance components.

1.1.2. Roles—Rasmitadila et al. (2022) explored the role of universities in mentoring programs for inclusive elementary schools, finding that effective instruction systems and resource centers are crucial. Toh et al. (2022) discussed mentoring’s role in professional identity formation for medical trainees, noting overlaps with role modeling, supervision, and coaching. Krishna et al. (2019) suggested viewing these practices under a ‘mentoring umbrella.’ Squires (2019) highlighted the emotional support mentors provide to early career teachers, which aids retention. Hayes (2019) found that mentoring helps new principals become effective learning leaders. Kuperminc (2020) demonstrated that group mentoring enhances academic resilience in at-risk high school students.

1.1.3. Benefits—Bustin (2022) emphasized professional development rewards for mentors in geography education. Tonna (2019) highlighted positive relationships and professional growth from mentoring in Maltese schools. Altonji et al. (2019) identified psychosocial and academic benefits of peer mentoring for medical students. Johnson et al. (2023) stressed the transformative impact of mentoring on careers and professional culture. Aderibigbe et al. (2022) examined mentoring challenges in teacher education across different countries. Dutton et al. (2022) found that mentor self-disclosure positively impacts youth mentoring relationships.

1.1.4. Obstacles—Njenga (2023) noted limited mentoring practices in Kenya’s vocational education sector, recommending structured guidelines and training. Purnamasari (2023) highlighted the need for proactive measures to promote positive attitudes towards mentoring. Mathew and Hakrob (2022) assessed a coaching program in Oman, identifying cultural and trust issues. Medegård et al. (2022) discussed successes and obstacles in mentoring newly arrived students in upper-secondary schools. Azzahra et al. (2022) examined the challenges of online learning. Sánchez et al. (2022) explored the support of undocumented Mexican youth by adult role models amidst educational inequality.

1.1.5. School Organizational Innovation—Robbins (2021) argued that organizational innovation enhances performance through product, process, and service improvements. Hodge et al. (2019) emphasized systematic changes in organizational structures. Daft (2018) categorized innovation into administrative and technical types. School innovation, according to Daft and Becker (2018), involves both educational and administrative aspects. Lee (2018) proposed that technical innovation relates to technologies and processes, while administrative innovation pertains to management strategies. Yen and Chang (2020) identified key dimensions of school innovation, including leadership, administrative operations, and curriculum development.

1.1.6. Teacher Expertise Development—García Weiss (2019) highlighted the need to recognize classroom teachers as experts. Cherng Halpin (2019) emphasized the importance of professional learning and growth for teacher experts, particularly for BIPOC teachers. Dana Yendol-Hoppey (2019) called for supportive structures to retain teachers and promote their expertise.

1.1.7. Resource Application Innovation—Resource application involves fostering school-

community relationships and securing resources for innovative measures. Effective communication strategies are vital for promoting organizational efficiency (Brinia et al., 2022; Fernandez Shaw, 2020). Engaging multiple communication channels ensures consistent and accessible messaging.

1.1.8. Campus Construction—Campus construction innovation focuses on enhancing the physical and aesthetic aspects of the learning environment to inspire creativity (Emmer Stough, 2021; Fisher, 2021). Upgraded classrooms with advanced technology can improve student engagement and learning outcomes (Conway, 2020; Troop, 2020).

1.2. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on one prominent theory in the realm of school organizational innovation the concept of “design thinking.” Originating from the field of product design, design thinking has gained traction in education as a method for fostering creativity, problem-solving, and innovation (Brown, 2018). This approach emphasizes empathy for end-users, such as students, teachers, and parents, and encourages iterative prototyping and testing to develop solutions that address their needs (Kelley Kelley, 2023). By adopting a design thinking mindset, schools can reframe challenges as opportunities for innovation and cultivate a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation. Another theory relevant to school organizational innovation is “organizational learning.” This theory posits that schools can become more effective by creating environments that facilitate ongoing learning and knowledge creation among staff and students (Argyris Schön, 2018). Organizational learning involves information sharing, reflection, and experimentation, which enable schools to identify and implement innovative practices that enhance teaching and learning outcomes. By embracing a culture of organizational learning, schools can become more agile and responsive to changing educational needs

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

and societal demands. Furthermore, the learning organization's history offers insights into how schools can achieve sustainable innovation. As proposed by Senge (2020), the learning organization is characterized by its capacity to continuously transform and adapt in response to external and internal pressures. Key principles include fostering systems thinking, promoting personal mastery, encouraging shared vision, and supporting team learning. By cultivating these

organizational capabilities, schools can create environments where innovation flourishes, enabling them to remain relevant and effective in an ever-evolving educational landscape. The model presented in Figure 1 showed the presumed relationships of the independent variable technical assistance on school organizational innovation in Oriental District, Digos City Division.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual paradigm; the arrow represents the significant relationship between the two variables. The right box represents the independent variable mentioned by Ganser (2018) to evaluate the technical assistance of teachers in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles. School organizational innovation serves as a dependent variable with five (5) indicators, as mentioned by Hsiao et al. (2019),

including the curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activity, teacher expertise development, resource application, and campus construction.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—This study examined the technical assistance and the school's organizational innovation. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of technical assistance of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) roles;
 - (2) benefits and;
 - (3) obstacles?
- (2) What is the extent of the school's organizational innovation in terms of:
 - (1) curriculum and instruction;
 - (2) school counseling and activity;
 - (3) teacher expertise development;

- (4) resource application and;
- (5) campus construction?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between the technical assistance of teachers and School organizational innovation?
- (4) Which of the domains of technical assistance of teachers significantly influence the school's organizational innovation?

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between technical assistance and school organizational innovation. H02: None of the domains of technical assistance significantly influence the school's organizational innovation. This study focused on the relationship between technical assistance and school organizational innovation. Public School District Supervisors. This study helped them design programs that helped teachers deliver effective teaching and learning processes. They can provide the appropriate technical assistance and proper mechanisms for monitoring school programs. The findings of this study served as the basis for planning, monitoring, and evalu-

ating school performance. School Heads. The study helped them in planning for the betterment of curriculum delivery and the welfare of the learners. The school heads could use the results of the study to provide technical assistance to teachers to ensure high learner outcomes. Teachers. The study's results helped teachers determine factors that affect learner outcomes. The findings served as a baseline to understand that teachers play a crucial role as the frontline in promoting learner outcomes in school. Learners. The beneficiary of this study helped learners receive appropriate intervention in the new normal. Future researchers. This study may serve as a valuable data source and as a basis for further study.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive research method, the primary tool of which was the adapted and modified standardized survey questionnaire, to determine the significant relationship between technical assistance and school organizational innovation. According to Calmorin (1995), as cited by Changiz et al. (2020), a descriptive

survey is used when the objective of the study is to seek a specific picture of the population under investigation in terms of their social and economic characteristics, opinions, and their knowledge about, or behavior toward a certain phenomenon. In this study, the researcher employed the quantitative descriptive type using the correlation analysis method. Descriptive research is quantitative research that involves

careful descriptions of educational phenomena (Gall Borg, 2017). This research design has limited control over extraneous variables, no independent variable manipulation, and is susceptible to threats and internal validity. Quantitative research is a formal, objective, systematic process using numerical data to obtain information about the world. Bryman (2016), as cited by (Smith, 2020), defines quantitative descriptive research as a methodological approach focused on describing the characteristics of a population or phenomenon through numerical data analysis. This type of research aims to provide a comprehensive overview and statistical summary of the variables under investigation without attempting to establish causal relationships. It typically involves collecting structured data using standardized measurement instruments, such as surveys or questionnaires and employs statistical techniques to analyze and interpret the data. The primary goal of quantitative descriptive research is to accurately portray the distribution, patterns, and trends within a given population or sample. Moreover, Stevens (2019) emphasizes the importance of descriptive research in providing factual and systematic data about a population or phenomenon. He highlights the use of statistical techniques such as averages, frequencies, and other summary measures to accurately describe the data's characteristics. Stevens' work aligns with the notion that descriptive research aims to acquire precise and factual information that could be utilized for statistical analysis and interpretation.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The 110 elementary teachers of Oriental District, Digos City Division, were the study's respondents. They have been in the service for three (3) years and are deemed to be Plantilla teachers who were randomly selected. The sample size was obtained using the Slovin formula. Slovin's Formula was used as my statistical technique to determine the sample size necessary for my population. After getting the sample size, I used the

fishbowl technique. In his technique, I randomly picked out my respondents from the fishbowl of all teachers in their respective schools. These employees were considered the respondents of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from the studies of Ganser (2018) and Hsiao et al. (2019), which were modified to suit the concept, place, situation, and ideas of the present study. The draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. The final copy of the research survey questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts for approval. The final revision was made by incorporating all the corrections, comments, and suggestions the experts gave before distribution and administration. The draft of the questionnaire was presented and evaluated by some expert validators. A standard evaluation tool was provided to them to rate, comment, and suggest improvement and development of the questionnaire. The results of the validation, together with the draft of the research instrument, were submitted to the research adviser for comments and suggestions. The ambiguous items were deleted; the weak items were strengthened and improved. After correction and refinement, the research instrument was returned to the researcher for finalization. The pilot testing was conducted in Oriental District, Digos City, and the respondents were not included in the research survey. The pilot testing was purposely conducted to establish the reliability and validity of the test instrument. The questionnaire was designed and modified to suit the needs of the respondents. Cronbach's alpha 0.08 was calculated to determine the reliability and validity of the survey questionnaire after taking a score from each scale item and correlating it with the total score for each observation. The resulting correlations are then compared with the variance for all individual item scores. This study used adapted and modi-

fied questionnaires. The first set was designed to gather information concerning the extent of technical assistance in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles. The second set is designed to gather data on the school’s organizational innovation in terms of curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activity, teacher expertise

development, resource application, and campus construction innovation in Oriental District, Digos City Division. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of technical assistance. The following interpretations of the data are found below.

Scale Rating	Descriptive	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Technical assistance for teachers is always provided.
3.41 – 4.20	Extensive	Technical assistance for teachers is oftentimes provided.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	Technical assistance for teachers is sometimes provided.
1.80 – 2.60	Less Extensive	Technical assistance for teachers is rarely provided.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Technical assistance for teachers is not provided.

The five-point Likert scale was used in this study to describe school organizational innovation:

Scale Rating	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school’s organizational innovation is always manifested.
3.41 – 4.20	Extensive	The school’s organizational innovation is oftentimes manifested.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The school’s organizational innovation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.60	Less Extensive	The school’s organizational innovation is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school’s organizational innovation is not manifested.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher followed the following procedures in this study. Permission to conduct the study. The necessary data were gathered on January 8, 2024, through the following procedure: The researcher asked permission from the office of

the Schools Division Superintendent of Digos City Division to conduct an online survey of the teachers of Oriental District. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the principals and supervisors of public schools in Ori-

ental District for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. The arrangement was made with the school principals and supervisors upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Distribution and retrieval of survey questionnaire An endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was given to the graduate student on November 18, 2023, for the approval of the division superintendent. A letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the concerned gender and development coordinators was prepared for easy data collection on January 8, 2024. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the research, conducted the survey, and retrieved the data through an online platform. The survey questionnaire was sent through the respondents' email, and once answered, it was sent to the researcher's email. The principals secured a received copy of the letter presented to vouch that the researcher had honestly conducted and collected the data from the study participants online. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The data gathered on January 8, 2024, was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially and accordingly. The study's results were analyzed and interpreted based on its purpose.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided to help

them better understand the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that the respondent's involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, the researcher did not force them. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote the students' learning interest to teachers' correlative teaching approach and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents were students, so they were considered vulnerable since all of them were not yet of legal age. They were also considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural source of information, to protect the respondents' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and adequately the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the

respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. The researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire to minimize inconvenience. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used, and the null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 significance level. The data were gathered, tallied, and treated using the Sta-

tistical Package for Social Sciences. Mean. The weighted arithmetic mean applies to options of different weights (Calmorin, 1998). This study used this statistical tool to measure the extent of technical assistance and school organizational innovation. Pearson's r . The person product-moment of the correlation coefficient was a linear correlation to find the degree of the association of two sets of variables (Calmorin, 1998). This study used this statistical tool to determine the significant relationship between technical assistance and school organizational innovation of the Digos City Division. Simple Linear Regression Analysis. The simple regression analysis was used to determine the domains of technical assistance that significantly influence the school's organizational innovation. It was a statistical method used to model the relationship between two continuous variables: one independent variable (predictor variable) and one dependent variable (outcome variable). It assumes that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussions of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: technical assistance and school organizational innovation.

3.1. The extent of technical assistance in terms of roles—Table 1 shows data on teachers' level of technical assistance in terms of roles. The presentation focuses on the highest and lowest mean ratings obtained, which are as follows: Provides links to other personnel in the school (4.78) and informs teachers about policies, procedures, and paperwork (2.01). Most of the items under the indicators garnered mean reorganizing extensively, which means that the level of mentoring in terms of roles was manifested. Collectively, the overall mean registered 3.76

or moderately extensive. This means that the respondents were able to comply with the order of integrating teachers' technical assistance in terms of roles, which were sometimes manifested. The provision of technical assistance showed that a good mentor is willing to share their knowledge and meet the mentees wherever they are in their professional journey. The best mentors can put themselves back in their trainees' shoes. The results show two main themes, namely university involvement, and inclusive education resource centers. The roles

of universities in mentoring programs for inclusive elementary schools are the development of effective instruction systems and the provision of human resources competent at implementing inclusive education in inclusive elementary schools.

Table 1. The extent of Technical Assistance of Teachers in terms of roles

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Provide support and encouragement to teachers	4.00	Very Extensive
2	Inform about policies, procedures, and paperwork to teachers	2.01	Less Extensive
3	Inform about school culture and expectations to teachers	2.07	Less Extensive
4	Help with lesson plans and material with discipline and classroom management	4.00	Extensive
5	Provide links to other personnel in the school	4.78	Very Extensive
6	Inform about job, benefits, insurance, and extracurricular activities	4.00	Extensive
7	Help with teaching skills and grading performance-making	4.00	Extensive
8	Meet with teacher-mentee regularly	4.40	Extensive
9	Provide information about special education offerings	4.00	Extensive
10	Observe teacher-mentee performances in teaching	4.40	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		3.76	Extensive

Rasmitadila et al. (2022) support the finding that the key problem with implementing inclusive education in inclusive elementary schools in Indonesia is that the role of all stakeholders in creating mentoring programs must be continuous and sustainable. Strong relationships between school staff members are essential for creating a collaborative and supportive environment where students can thrive. Teachers, in particular, are at the heart of student learning and well-being. This researcher emphasizes the significance of solid relationships among different school staff members in fostering a collaborative and supportive environment. Inclusive education is not the responsibility of a single individual or group; instead, it requires collective action and shared ownership among teachers, support staff, administrators, and other school personnel. The study’s findings confirm Toh et

al.’s (2022) assertion that mentoring plays a critical role in nurturing professional identity formation. Teachers need to be well informed about school policies and procedures to effectively fulfill their roles and responsibilities. This ensures consistency, compliance, and overall efficiency within the school environment, ultimately creating a smoother learning experience for students. Teacher effectiveness hinges on professional development (as shown by research) and their familiarity with school policies and procedures. This knowledge creates a well-organized and efficient school environment, fostering a smoother learning experience for teachers and students.

3.2. *The extent of technical assistance in terms of Benefits*—Presented in Table 2 are data on the level of technical assistance in terms of benefits. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which

are as follows: provides support and encouragement to the teacher-mentee (4.24) gives reflection and introspection to new ideas and feelings to the teacher-mentee (4.24) provides new ideas and renewal concepts of learning (3.42) and establish learning about policies, and procedures, for teacher-mentee (3,42). All items under the indicator of course communication garnered mean results of extensive with means

that technical assistance in terms of its benefits was oftentimes provided. Collectively, the overall mean of 3.79 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive means that technical assistance in terms of benefits was oftentimes provided. This means that the technical assistance of teachers oftentimes improves their skills, and they get better. Makes it clear that they care about their employees' growth and learning.

Table 2. The extent of Technical Assistance of Teachers in terms of benefits

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Provide support and encouragement to the teacher-mentee	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Provide new ideas and renewal concepts of learning	3.42	Extensive
3	Guide teacher-mentee for satisfaction in helping someone's achievement	3.94	Extensive
4	Give resources to fit into new concepts and learning to teacher-mentee	3.77	Extensive
5	Improve skills and get better, faster learning in mentoring teacher-mentee	3.59	Extensive
6	Give reflection and introspection to new ideas and feelings to teacher-mentee	4.24	Very Extensive
7	Establish learning about policies, and procedures, for teacher-mentee	3.42	Extensive
8	Give rapport relationship in teaching, smoother transition from work to school environment	3.94	Extensive
9	Establish learning more about colleagues in school and other schools/districts	3.77	Extensive
10	Set new roles, and responsibilities for teacher-mentee	3.59	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.79	Extensive

Brown (2018) corroborated the above finding. This means that by providing a supportive and nurturing environment, mentors help build the confidence and resilience of teacher-mentees, enabling them to tackle obstacles with determination and positivity. Mentors model professional behaviors, and so the extent to which geographical knowledge features in your professional identity will play a role in how you are seen and emulated. This highlighted that by

offering unwavering support and positive reinforcement, mentors help boost teacher-mentees' confidence, enabling them to tackle challenges with resilience and determination. mentors provide a valuable source of guidance for mentees as they encounter obstacles and seek to develop effective strategies for their classrooms. Beyond practical advice, mentors offer emotional support, creating a safe space for mentees to express their concerns and frustrations. The result

is in conjunction with Tonna's (2019) views that newly qualified teachers seek advice from more experienced colleagues and are considered to learn through participation, including observing other teachers and receiving feedback. In many education systems worldwide, induction programs are developed to support these new teachers in pedagogical and practical needs. This researcher advocates for a culture that encourages teacher-mentees to explore their thoughts, emotions, and reactions to new ideas, with mentors guiding them to develop a deeper understanding of their teaching beliefs, principles, and goals. Encouraging reflection and introspection among teacher-mentees is essential for nurturing their professional growth and increasing their impact in the classroom. This reflective approach enhances teaching effectiveness and cultivates a mindset of continuous learning and progress. This finding is supported by Altonji et al. (2019), who stated that by presenting new ideas and concepts of renewal, mentors inspire teacher-mentees to embrace innovation, adaptability, and creativity in their practice. Peer mentoring may be helpful for 1st-year medical students; however, little evidence is thus far available on which aspects of peer mentoring provide benefits and what those specific benefits are. This exposure to innovative teaching methods and evolving educational trends motivates teacher-mentees to broaden their instructional approaches, explore novel techniques, and commit to lifelong learning. Additionally, the integration of fresh concepts and rejuvenated ideas invigorates teaching methods, nurturing an atmosphere of innovation and ongoing enhancement within education. Dutton et al. (2022) remarked that by providing comprehensive instruction and clarification on policies and procedures, mentors equip teacher-mentees with the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate the complexities

of the educational system effectively. Little is known about the benefits of mentor disclosure or the ethics of adopting this communication approach because self-disclosure has not been thoroughly investigated within the framework of treatments based on youth-adult assisting relationships. It highlights the multifaceted nature of mentorship in education, encompassing the practical guidance on policies and procedures and the complex dynamics of interpersonal communication and relationship-building between mentors and mentees. By addressing these aspects comprehensively, mentorship programs can better support the professional development and well-being of teacher-mentees, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness as educators.

3.3. *The extent of technical assistance in terms of obstacles*—Table 3 displayed data on teachers' technical assistance in terms of obstacles. The presentation concentrates on the indicators with the rating obtained from the highest and lowest of the following: Sets goals of mentoring unclear and unrealistic ideas (3.68) and Guides in the mentor selection process in the school (3.68) and uplifts the negative attitude of other teachers or administrators toward mentoring (3.16). It secures mismatches between teacher-mentees and MTs regarding teaching assignments and ideology (3.16). The items under this indicator garnered extensive mean results, which means the teachers oftentimes manifested maximization of the evaluation result. The overall mean of 3.32 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive means that Teachers' preparedness in online teaching in the new normal in terms of time management is often manifested. Furthermore, the finding suggests that it is important to communicate learners' progress in improving their academic performance. Moreover, explaining their evaluation results to the learners encourages them to strive harder.

Table 3. The extent of Technical Assistance of Teachers in terms of obstacles

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Establish time for meetings and observations	3.27	Extensive
2	Seek time for conferences on personality conflicts between teacher-mentee	3.23	Moderately Extensive
3	Find time to solve the problems of lack of administrative support	3.25	Moderately Extensive
4	Secure mismatch between teacher-mentee and MTs in terms of teaching assignment and ideology	3.16	Moderately Extensive
5	Set goals for mentoring unclear and unrealistic ideas	3.68	Extensive
6	Enhance roles of teacher-mentee which is unclear to them	3.27	Extensive
7	Set teacher-mentee as an aspect of the school mentoring program	3.23	Moderately Extensive
8	Enhance the low commitment of teacher-mentee to uplift them	3.25	Moderately Extensive
9	Uplift the negative attitude of other teachers or administrators toward mentoring	3.16	Moderately Extensive
10	Guide in the mentor selection process in the school	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.32	Moderately Extensive

The findings aligned with Njenga’s (2023) statement that the Government of Kenya has recruited additional technical and vocational education and training elementary teachers to expand Kenya’s vocational education sector. It is expected that existing elementary teachers will mentor the new teachers. However, teacher mentorship practices in Kenya’s elementary education sector are under-researched, and it remains unclear what mentorship practices exist and how effective they are. This researcher examines how unclear or unrealistic mentoring goals undermine the effectiveness of the mentoring relationship and hamper the mentee’s progress. This lack of clarity leaves mentees unsure about their objectives and how to gauge their advancement. Consequently, they may struggle to stay focused and motivated in their professional development endeavors. Unrealistic goals, on the other hand, set mentees up for failure and disappointment as they may be unattainable within

the given parameters. This finding collaborates with the study of Purnamasari (2023), which explained that mentoring sometimes creates conflict between teachers, which makes the implementation slow. It has been widely applied to professional development practices in many areas. Johnson et al. (2023) cited the obstacles of mentoring as the low commitment of teacher-mentees to uplift their perception of the process. Therefore, it is essential to recognize and address these mismatches through open communication, mutual understanding, and collaboration. By acknowledging and reconciling differences in teaching assignments and ideologies, mentors and mentees can work together more effectively towards shared goals, fostering a supportive and enriching mentorship experience. Purnamasari (2023) explained that mentoring has been widely applied to professional development practices in many areas, including education. it becomes imperative for mentors to uplift

and shift these negative attitudes through proactive measures. Mentors can achieve this by highlighting the benefits of mentoring, such as professional growth, improved teaching practices, and enhanced student outcomes. The findings underscore the importance of examining and potentially adapting successful professional development practices from other countries to address educators' specific needs and challenges in different contexts. It also emphasizes the potential benefits of implementing mentoring programs for English foreign language teachers in Indonesia, such as promoting collaboration, sharing best practices, and enhancing teacher effectiveness.

3.4. *Summary on the extent of technical assistance of teachers*—Table 4 displays the data on the summary of technical assistance of teachers. The overall mean of the data in this table is 3.76. The indicators are presented from highest to lowest with the corresponding mean: roles (4.16) and obstacles (3.32). Two of the indicators are with the mean descriptive equivalent of extensive. However, the indicators of obstacles have a mean descriptive equivalent of moderately extensive. The extensive mean rating in this study suggests that teachers' technical assistance is often manifested, which means that it addresses the professional needs of teachers' coaching ability in the classroom.

Table 4. Summary on the extent of technical assistance of teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Roles	3.76	Extensive
Benefits	3.79	Extensive
Obstacles	3.32	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.62	Extensive

The results depicted in Table 4 are supported by Handrianto et al. (2022). This study discusses two important variables in teachers' role as educators in elementary school institutions: mentoring and professional development. Mentoring is believed to help teachers enhance their teaching quality and involvement with students. Professional development refers to teachers' skills in implementing activities in their teaching-learning process. The study's results confirm that five factors contribute to the implementation of a mentoring strategy for teachers' professional development in elementary school: the teamwork approach, Teachers' attitude, Exchange of information, Continuous learning, and improvement of Teaching skills. The study concludes that a mentoring strategy significantly improves teachers' professional development

during their educational services. Mentoring is not limited to novice teachers; it should be applied to all teachers as a manifestation of life-long learning. Medegård et al. (2022) presented new knowledge arising from teachers' verbal accounts of successes and obstacles in upper-secondary schools' organizational and practical work with newly arrived students. The analysis reveals several dimensions contributing to the construction and reconstruction of successes and obstacles in the teachers' accounts. Teachers are constructed as actors with a power advantage relative to the "newly arrived student." The study highlights the power dynamics at play within the teacher-student relationship. Teachers are portrayed as having a power advantage relative to newly arrived students, which may impact how they perceive and respond to chal-

lenges. This imbalance of power underscores the importance of promoting equity and inclusivity in education, ensuring that all students, including newly arrived ones, receive the support and resources they need to succeed.

3.5. *The extent of school organizational innovation In terms of curriculum and instruction*—Indicated in Table 5 is the extent of school organizational innovation in terms of curricu-

lum and instruction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Made use or share creative teaching materials I developed (4.30), while innovating lessons by integrating creativity for the learners according to their needs (4.18) is often manifested, which means extensive. The overall mean rating of curriculum and instruction is 4.25, or very extensive.

Table 5. The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of Curriculum and instruction

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Innovate lessons by integrating creativity for the learners according to their needs.	4.18	Extensive
2.	Made use of or shared creative teaching materials I developed.	4.30	Very Extensive
3.	Emphasized the integration of creative thinking with teaching content.	4.24	Very Extensive
4.	Used diversified teaching methods to facilitate learning.	4.29	Very Extensive
5.	Established a platform for the sharing of results and experiences in innovative education.	4.26	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.25	Very Extensive

This means that the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division, always manifest the extent of school organizational innovation. This indicates that the schools exhibit extensive implementation mechanisms for improving organizational innovation. This finding is supported by Weller (2018). Scholars have increasingly explored the application of Digital Pedagogy in curriculum and instruction, which integrates technology to enhance learning experiences. Digital Pedagogy emphasizes the use of digital tools and resources to promote active engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking among learners. This researcher ex-

amines how the use of teaching materials can enhance your sense of ownership and investment in your teaching practice. It provides an opportunity for creativity and innovation, allowing you to experiment with different approaches and refine your instructional techniques over time. As you see the positive impact of your materials on student learning outcomes, it can also boost your confidence and motivation as an educator. This study confirmed the study of CAST (2018). The Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework has gained attention for its emphasis on designing flexible and accessible curricula and instruction to meet the

diverse needs of all learners, including those with disabilities. However, incorporating real-world connections and problem-solving tasks into lessons can inspire creativity and critical thinking among learners. By presenting authentic challenges and opportunities for application, educators can encourage students to think innovatively and apply their knowledge and skills to solve meaningful problems.

3.6. *The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of school counseling and activities*—Table 6 presents the extent of school organizational innovation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Designed creativity of life counseling measures for students (4.41), Created a program for an after-school counseling system (2.20), are often manifested, thus extensive in their implementation.

Table 6. The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of school counseling and activities

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Organized annual problem-solving or creative competitive events for students.	4.17	Extensive
2.	Established procedures that govern students' participation in various innovative club activities.	4.08	Extensive
3.	Created life counseling measures for students.	2.20	Less Extensive
4.	Designed creativity of life counseling measures for students.	4.41	Very Extensive
5.	Created a program for an after-school counseling system.	4.15	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.80	Extensive

The overall mean rating of school counseling and activities is 3.80 or extensive. This means that the extent of school organizational innovation in terms of school counseling and activities is often manifested by the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division. This indicates that the schools are exhibiting extensive implementation mechanisms to continuously improve school organizational innovation. This finding is supported by Dahir and Stone (2019). New standards in K-12 education and new comprehensive school counseling programs established at national and state lev-

els promote and enhance student achievement and success to a large extent. Despite the increased focus on academic improvement, the school counseling profession is omitted from most educational reforms. Moreover, the insight into designing creative life counseling measures for students underscores the importance of flexibility, empathy, and innovation in meeting their diverse needs and fostering holistic development. Through thoughtful and creative interventions, counselors can empower students to overcome challenges, build resilience, and thrive in all aspects of their lives. Accord-

ing to the ASCA (2018), the professional school counseling services model makes them uniquely qualified to address all students’ academic, career, and personal/social development needs by designing, implementing, evaluating, and enhancing a comprehensive school counseling program that promotes and enhances student success. This researcher pointed out that the majority of counselors expressed a concern that the current school system is not aligned with their expectations for their students. They called for reform, including empowerment for leadership, reduced administrative tasks, smaller caseloads, and accountability.

3.7. *The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of teacher expertise development*—Table 7 reveals the extent of school

organizational innovation regarding teacher expertise development. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Establishing procedure governing teachers’ engagement in action research (4.38); meanwhile, offered learning that promotes innovativeness of students within and across learning result (4.00). The overall mean rating of teacher expertise development is 4.26 or very extensive. This means that the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division always manifest the extent of school organizational innovation regarding teacher expertise development. This indicates that the schools exhibit pervasive implementation, considering various tasks implemented.

Table 7. The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of teacher expertise development

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Offered learning that promotes innovativeness of students within and across learning results.	4.00	Extensive
2.	Established procedure governing teachers’ engagement in action research.	4.38	Very Extensive
3.	Encouraged teachers to take part in innovative learning.	4.35	Very Extensive
4.	Exhibited an updated recruitment mechanism that is consistent with DepEd policy.	4.28	Very Extensive
5.	Instituted innovative procedures that would encourage teachers to pursue further professional development.	4.33	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.26	Very Extensive

This is confirmed in the study by Cherng and Halpin (2019). The specialized knowledge needed by classroom teachers is a core component of who teacher experts are. However,

teacher experts also pursue further professional learning, growth, and leadership opportunities that extend beyond the teaching and learning inside their classrooms and into their schools,

districts, communities, and professions at large. Teachers begin by identifying a research question or area of inquiry that aligns with their interests, classroom practices, and areas for improvement. This question should be specific, relevant, and actionable, allowing for focused investigation and meaningful outcomes. The above findings confirmed (Cherng Halpin, 2019) that a vital part of supporting teacher expertise is creating sustainable structures that encourage teachers to stay in classrooms to develop their expertise. educators can leverage technology and digital tools to promote innovativeness among students. Ultimately, providing educational opportunities that encourage creativity within and across learning objectives equips students to embrace lifelong learning and innovation. By cultivating an environment of innovation within classrooms, educators equip students with the skills needed to navigate the complexities of an ever-evolving world. This prepares them

to make meaningful contributions to society through their inventive thinking and problem-solving abilities.

3.8. *The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of resource application—* Table 8 presents the extent of school organizational innovation regarding resource application. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Introducing community resources to assist in promoting various innovative activities (4.26) Succeed in securing budget and resources from other external sources (3.10) are oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive in their effectiveness. The overall mean rating of resource application is 3.91 or moderately extensive. This means that the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division oftentimes manifest the extent of school organizational innovation in terms of resource application.

Table 8. The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of resource application

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Established innovative mechanism that encourages students to acquire technical qualifications	4.07	Extensive
2.	Succeed in securing budget and resources from other external sources	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3.	Teaching – learning processes improvement	4.03	Extensive
4.	Introduced community resources to assist in promoting various innovative activities	4.26	Very Extensive
5.	Inclined participation of alumni to participate in innovative operation-related activities	4.11	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.91	Extensive

This is confirmed in the study of (Brinia et al., 2022) Effective community presupposes

an open communication climate that provides security to people and will encourage them to

take initiatives aimed at improving the functioning of the organization. In this climate, community resources such as libraries, community centers, and environmental organizations can offer students opportunities for research, exploration, and community engagement. The principal of each educational organization, as the first among equals in the teachers' association, is a decisive factor in shaping a supportive community. Incorporating community resources into educational activities enriches learning experiences, fostering authenticity and relevance. This approach encourages collaboration and civic involvement among students, motivating them to contribute to their communities actively. Moreover, these partnerships facilitate connections between classroom learning and the real world, instilling a sense of belonging and empowerment in students as they recognize the broader impact of their education. This finding is supported by (Fernandez Shaw, 2020) By effectively securing funding from external sources, educational institutions can access additional resources and opportunities to enrich students'

learning experiences. Early communication can help reduce fear and encourage the community to respond positively to the school policies implemented. This researcher emphasizes the importance of strategic planning, communication, and collaboration in securing funding and implementing effective policies to support student learning and success in educational settings. By leveraging external resources and engaging stakeholders in decision-making, schools can create a supportive and enriching learning environment for all students.

3.9. *The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of campus construction*— Table 9 presents the extent of school organizational innovation regarding classroom construction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Providing library resources for teachers and learners (4.39) while Planning campus public space that would inspire creativity in students (4.00) is always manifested thus, extensive in its effectiveness.

Table 9. The extent of school organizational innovation in terms of campus construction

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Planned campus public space that would inspire creativity in students.	4.00	Extensive
2.	Decorated classroom learning environment that would inspire creativity in learners.	4.29	Very Extensive
3.	Has the capacity to reconstruct classroom functions to cater to the needs for innovative education.	4.33	Very Extensive
4.	Provided necessary equipment and space that teachers need for innovative teaching.	4.32	Very Extensive
5.	Provided library resources for teachers and learners	4.39	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.26	Very Extensive

The overall mean rating of resource application is 4.26, which is very extensive. This means that the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division manifest the extent of school organizational innovation in terms of classroom construction. This indicates that the schools are exhibiting very extensive implementation of school organizational innovation, considering various tasks implemented in the schools. The above findings are confirmed by Emmer Stough (2019). Teachers’ ability to organize classrooms and manage their students’ behavior is critical to achieving positive educational outcomes. Teachers can utilize library materials to stay updated on current educational trends, explore new teaching strategies, and enhance their subject knowledge. However, providing library resources for teachers and learners enriches the educational experience, fostering a culture of intellectual curiosity, exploration, and lifelong learning within educational institutions. By investing in library resources and services, institutions demonstrate their commitment to supporting the academic success and holistic development of their students and educators alike. Young et al. (2019) stress the importance of the physical environment and note that student achievement is impacted by such factors as lighting, noise, and climate control. The authors also describe student perception of the physical environment, noting that students as

young as elementary school age are aware of the physical attributes of their learning environment and have a sense of whether the environment is appropriately updated and conducive to learning. This researcher summarizes the importance of the physical environment to educational achievement by detailing the existing links in the research literature between classroom conditions and learning. The significant effect of classroom environment on concentration levels, listening, and writing is supported by research results that have found higher test scores and more positive student outlooks in upgraded learning environments.

3.10. *Summary of the extent of school organizational innovation*—Table 10 summarizes the extent of school organizational innovation in terms of curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activities, teacher expertise development, and resource application among schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division. The result is focused on teacher expertise development (4.26) and Classroom construction (4.26), which has the highest mean rating, and school counseling and activities (3.80), the lowest. The overall mean rating of 4.09 suggests that implementation of school organizational innovation is always manifested, thus very extensive, among Schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division.

Table 10. Summary of the extent of school organizational innovation

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Curriculum and instruction	4.25	Very Extensive
2.	School counseling and activities	3.80	Extensive
3.	Teacher expertise development	4.26	Very Extensive
4.	Resource application	3.91	Extensive
5.	Classroom construction	4.26	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.09	Very Extensive

This is confirmed in the study of Robbins (2019), who believes that true expertise, cultivated over years of classroom experience, ongoing professional development, and collaboration with colleagues, boosts organizational performance and that innovation includes product innovation, production technology innovation, structural innovation, management system innovation, and so forth. This researcher suggests that teacher expertise contributes to organizational performance by fostering innovation across various dimensions. Innovation in education encompasses not only curriculum and instructional methods but also structural changes, management systems, and technological integration. Experienced teachers are better equipped to innovate in their classrooms, implementing new approaches to engage students, personalize learning experiences, and improve outcomes. This finding is supported by Hodge et al. (2019), who suggested that classroom construction is an alternative for an organization in its current situation and may involve a systematic change of organizational system, input and output relationship, technological or conversion process, classroom construction or design, scheme of collaboration, organization personnel and their roles, and organizational culture and reforms of all aspects. In summary, the concept of classroom construction offers organizations a comprehensive framework for navigating change and driving improvement. By addressing multiple dimensions, including organizational systems, technological processes, physical spaces, collaboration schemes, personnel roles, and cultural norms, organizations can create an environment conducive to growth, innovation, and sustainable success. Each educational organization has its own culture that determines the school counseling and activities, such as the atmosphere and conditions within which ideas, information, actions, and feelings are exchanged. Effective school counseling presupposes an open communication climate that

provides security to people and will encourage them to take initiatives aimed at improving the functioning of the organization. In this climate, the activity members develop equal communication relationships with each other and learn to cooperate and understand each other. The principal of each educational organization, as the first among equals in the teachers' association, is a decisive factor in shaping a supportive communication climate (Brinia et al., 2022) In essence, this researcher highlights the importance of nurturing school counseling and activities within educational organizations. By fostering an environment where all members feel heard, respected, and empowered to contribute, schools can enhance their counseling practices and activities, ultimately promoting student success and well-being

3.11. Relationship between the extent of teachers' technical assistance and school organizational innovation—Shown in Table 11 are data about the significant relationship between teachers' technical assistance and school organizational innovation. Analyzing the data by Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r , the results are: the computed r -value for technical assistance versus school organizational innovation is 0.765 which denotes an almost substantial relationship or definite relationship. While computing the r -value, it is found as 4.41 with a probability value of 0.013 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between technical assistance and school organizational innovation. The greater the technical assistance, the greater the school's organizational innovation; hence, a positive correlation occurs when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. This mere example of linear correlation or straight-line relationships between two variables. A correlation can range between -1 (perfect negative relationship) and +1 (perfect positive relationship), with 0 indicating no straight-line relationship.

Table 11. Relationship between the extent of technical assistance and school organizational innovation

Variables	r-values	computed t-value	P value	Remarks/Decision
Technical Assistance (x)				
School Organizational Innovation (y)	0.765	4.41	0.013	Reject

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

Given the results, teachers’ technical assistance revealed relevance with school organizational innovation. The above findings affirmed what Tran (2020) reported that the provision of technical assistance to teachers is a dyadic relationship. It is also reported in the mentees and the mentors’ personal and professional development. In their research, Daft and Becker (2018) found that school innovation could be separated into educational innovation and administrative innovation, which manifest as education/course innovation and administrative management innovation, respectively. The former is implemented by teachers, usually in a bottom-up fashion. The degree of teachers’ professional competence is directly proportional to the likelihood of course/education innovation by teachers. As such, course and education innovation would become the necessary component for improving education efficacy. The latter is implemented by administrative personnel. This finding is supported by Yen and Chang (2020), who shape school organizational innovation through administrative management. The dimensions of school organizational innovation

vary according to the perspectives taken by researchers.

3.12. *Significant Influence of teacher’s technical assistance On school organizational innovation.*—Table 12 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence of teachers’ technical assistance on school organizational innovation in the Digos City Division. All indicators of the teacher’s technical assistance provided, namely obstacles (0.014), indicate a statistically significant influence on teacher-school organizational innovation. The benefits of being mentored include being encouraged and empowered in personal development, helping to identify and achieve career goals, and helping to identify and correct gaps in generic skills and knowledge. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.886 suggests that the teacher’s technical assistance accounts for 88.6 percent of the school’s organizational innovation variance. This provides empirical evidence that variability of the extent of confidence can be accounted for and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under the extent of teacher’s technical assistance in Digos City Division.

Table 12. Regression Coefficients and Model Summary

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standard Error	Standardized Coefficients	t	p	Decision
H (Intercept)	3.356	0.056		60.083	< .001	
H (Intercept)	0.167	0.157		1.069	0.287	
Roles	0.095	0.090	0.100	0.949	0.343	Accept
Benefits	0.131	0.092	0.157	1.444	0.151	Accept
Planning	0.213	0.092	0.256	2.461	0.014	*Reject
Model Summary						
R ²	0.760					
Value	112.443					
p-value	< .001					

In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (112.443) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, which indicates that the model is a better predictor of teachers' technical assistance. Thus, the teacher's technical assistance enabled the teacher's school's organizational innovation. The technical assistance of teachers in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles motivated teachers to do better in their craft. This is confirmed in the study by Lee (2018), which identified educational innovation, equipment resource innovation, organizational atmosphere innovation, and administrative operation innovation as the four dimensions of research on school organizational innovation. In other words, schools should provide new teaching equipment and

adopt new administrative operations to create an innovative atmosphere that would facilitate educational and organizational innovation. In addition, it would also guide teachers to apply innovative teaching methods and tools in their instruction to ultimately boost school performance. The professional development of teachers is in high demand in today's educational system. It does not particularly pertain to the certificate only achieved from seminars or even from conferences, but the outcome of how instructional coaches improved in terms of planning, time management, mastering deep knowledge about the subject matter, and flexibility for learners' needs, especially despite their differences. Innovation plays a fundamental role in improving school quality (Ubaidillah et al., 2018).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings are based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions. The following are the study's findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of technical assistance of teachers in terms of its indicators, namely, Roles (3.76), Benefits (3.79), and Obstacles (3.32). The overall mean rating of 3.62 suggests that technical assistance of teachers is often manifested, thus very extensive among schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division. The extent of school organizational innovation in curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activities, teacher expertise

development, resource application, and classroom management in Digos Oriental District, Digos City Division. Revealed teacher expertise development (4.26) and classroom management (4.26) exhibit always manifested, thus, very extensive. The overall mean rating of 4.09 suggests that school organizational innovation is always manifested among the schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of technical assistance of teachers' efficiency ($r=0.62$; $p<.001$) and school organizational innovation among schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division. All indicators of technical assistance of teachers are statistically significant in influencing school organizational innovation among schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the overall result of this research, the following conclusions are drawn: The finding reveals that teachers provide extensive technical assistance regarding roles, benefits, and obstacles. It is noted that teachers need mentors who are measurably aligned with the learning objectives and who will provide learners with opportunities for interaction. Mentors can develop leadership skills and gain a sense of satisfaction from knowing they have helped someone. Mentees can expand their knowledge and skills, gain valuable advice from a more experienced person, and build professional networks. The school organizational innovation in curriculum and instruction, school counseling and activities, teacher expertise development, resource application, and classroom management among schools in Oriental District, Digos City Division revealed curriculum and instruction, teacher expertise and development, and classroom management exhibits very extensive. In contrast, school counseling and activities and resource application exhibit extensiveness. There is a significant correlation between the extent of technical assistance and school organizational innovation in Oriental District, Digos City Division. The more effective the teachers' technical assistance, the higher their professional development; hence, a positive correlation occurs when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. Indicators of

continuous improvement programs are statistically significant in influencing school organizational innovation in Oriental District, Digos City Division.

4.2. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit: The Public School District Supervisor in Oriental District may comprehensively monitor the school innovations implemented that contribute to the academic achievement of learners with the utilization and maximization of resources to improve learning outcomes as policy inputs in the coming future. They may provide technical assistance to schools that did not maximize the resource application, counseling, and activities. School heads of Oriental District may sustain innovative practices to intensify the implementation of different innovations in schools. They should provide more avenues for teachers to intensify their technical assistance to their profession. Other factors that may influence school organizational innovation in terms of teachers' technical assistance to society and profession may be explored, and results utilized may be considered. Future research may include the underlying empirical investigations on other processes and mechanisms of school organizational innovation practices through more profound technical assistance to improve professional growth and enhance the school's performance.

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